

Electrokinetic Potential (ζ) of Oil Droplets Dispersed in the Aqueous Solutions of Long Chain Electrolytes

Lalita Kundu* and B. N. Ghosh

The electrophoretic mobility of oil droplets has been measured under conditions in which the concentration of the long chain electrolyte in the aqueous phase is varied while the ionic strength is kept constant. Using these data the values of zeta-potential have been evaluated with a view to ascertain its dependence on the number of stabilizing ions adsorbed per unit area of the interface and hence on the concentration of the long chain electrolyte in the aqueous phase.

In the present investigation, the electrophoretic mobility of oil droplets dispersed in the aqueous solutions of long chain electrolytes such as cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and sodium dodecyl sulphate (NaDS) has been measured by the microcataphoretic method¹. The adsorbed amount of the stabilizing ion per unit area of the interface has been evaluated using Gibbs isotherm in the form $\Gamma = -\frac{1}{RT} \cdot \frac{d\gamma}{d \ln c}$ since in our experiments there has always been present a sufficient excess of added neutral electrolyte to keep the ionic strength constant. The dependence of zeta-potential (ζ) on the adsorbed amount Γ in gm-ion/cm² and hence on the concentration of the stabilizing ion in the aqueous phase has been discussed in the light of the experimental data.

Many authors²⁻⁸ have worked with problems of similar interest.

EXPERIMENTAL

Measurement of electrophoretic mobility (U_a): The procedure adopted is the same as that described by Chakrabarty and Ghosh^{1,2}.

The microcataphoretic cell with its plane vertical and the axis of the microscope horizontal has been used by Bull⁶ in 1958 and has been adopted for our measurement with some further modifications.

* Department of Chemistry, Vidyasagar College for Women, Calcutta-6.

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The position of the stationary layer in the flat cell has been determined by Komagata⁹ and on the basis of his result, the velocity of the droplets in the stationary layer at 0.2 d has been measured where d represents depth of the cell. The ratio of the width : depth in the cell used by us is 10 : 1.

The observed mobility (U_a) of the droplet which traverses a distance ' d ' cm. in t seconds under the potential gradient ' E ' is given by

$$U_a = \frac{d}{t.E} = \frac{d}{t \left(\frac{i}{S.A.} \right)} = \frac{d.S.A.}{i.t} = \frac{d.k.A.}{i.R.t.}$$

where, A = Area of the cross-section of the microcataphoretic cell = 0.2517 sq. cm. in our apparatus.

S = Specific bulk conductance of the solution, = $\frac{k}{R}$ where k = cell constant of the conductance cell and R = observed resistance and i = current in ampere.

Purity of the constituents : Purity of NaDS and CTAB has been discussed previously^{10,11}. NaCl and HCl used are guaranteed reagents, and have been found free from surfactant impurities by surface tension measurements. Oils used are benzene, toluene, n -heptane and liquid paraffin. Benzene, toluene and n -heptane are products of E. Merck and redistilled. Liquid paraffin of B.P. quality has been used without further purification.

Preparation of the emulsion : The stock emulsion has been prepared by shaking and homogenizing 10 ml. of oil with 100 ml. of water and then 5 ml. of this emulsion have been diluted to 100 ml. with the aqueous solution of the desired long chain electrolyte. Ionic strengths are adjusted at a constant value with NaCl, NaCl and HCl only. All the emulsions have been prepared keeping the ratio of oil in water constant and only the concentration of the long chain ion in the aqueous phase has been varied.

Evaluation of ζ : For each concentration of the stabilizing ion electrophoretic mobility of a fairly large number of droplets have been measured and their average (U_a) has been taken. From these data the values of ζ -potential have been calculated by using the equation

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta}{D} \cdot U_a \times (300)^2 \text{ mV.}$$

Since in our experiments ionic strengths have always been maintained either at 0.01 (NaCl or HCl) or greater than 0.01 [such as 0.02 and 0.03] and oil droplets dispersed are of radius not less than 1×10^{-4} cm. as they are clearly visible with a magnification of 250 times only; so no correction for the relaxation or surface conductance effect is necessary^{12,13}.

9. S. Komagata, Quoted in Abramson *et al.* "Electrophoresis of proteins and Chemistry of cell surfaces", Reinhold, New York, 1942.
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12. J. T. Davies and E. K. Rideal, "Electrophoresis discussed in Interfacial Phenomena", 2nd Ed., 1963, Academic Press, New York.
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The values of ζ calculated are recorded in the Tables I to VII.

TABLE I

Benzene-water-NaDS

Ionic strength = 0.01; maintained by adding NaCl

Temperature = 25°; $\eta_{25}^{\circ} = 0.008937$ poise; $D_{25}^{\circ} = 78^{\circ}$

$R = 0.17 \times 10^3$ ohms.; $k =$ cell constant = 0.18; $i = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ ampere;

$A = 0.2517$ sq. cm.

Concentration of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^5$	Average electro-phoretic mobility (U_a) in cm/sec/volt/cm. $U_a \times 10^4$	Adsorbed amount of NaDS in gm-ion per 1 cm^2 of the interface $\Gamma \times 10^{10}$	ζ in mV
1.0	8.29	—	107.5
2.0	8.95	—	116.0
3.0	9.58	0.945	124.2
4.0	9.82	1.04	127.4
8.0	10.41	1.27	135.0
10.0	10.58	1.36	137.2
18.3	11.10	1.58	143.9

TABLE II

Toluene-water-NaDS

Ionic strength = 0.01 (maintained by adding NaCl)

Temperature = 25°; $R = 0.15 \times 10^3$ ohms.; $i = 1.5 \times 10^3$ ampere.

Concentration of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^5$	Average U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm. $U_a \times 10^4$	$\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ in gm-ion	ζ in mV
0.90	9.13	0.631	118.4
1.83	9.35	0.771	121.2
2.74	9.66	0.912	125.2
3.65	9.82	0.969	127.4
4.50	10.02	1.052	130.0
9.13	10.47	1.37	135.7
18.30	10.95	1.67	141.9
27.40	11.44	1.84	148.4

TABLE III

Liquid paraffin-water-NaDS

Ionic strength = 0.01 (maintained by NaCl)

Temperature = 25°; $R = 0.15 \times 10^3$ ohms; $i = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ amp.

Concentration of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^5$	Average U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm. $U_a \times 10^4$	$\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ in gm-ion	ζ in mV
2.5	9.68	1.15	125.5
3.0	9.82	1.25	127.4
5.0	10.50	1.62	136.1
7.5	10.95	2.05	141.9
9.0	11.44	2.26	148.4
10.0	11.44	2.41	148.4
12.5	11.68	—	151.4

TABLE IV

n-Heptane-water-NaDS

Ionic strength = 0.01 (maintained by adding NaCl)

Temperature = 25°; $R = 0.15 \times 10^3$ ohms; $i = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ amp.

Concentration of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^4$	Average U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm. $U_a \times 10^4$	$\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ in gm-ion	ζ in mV
1.50	8.51	2.72	110.4
2.00	8.67	2.89	112.4
2.50	8.95	3.16	116.1
4.00	9.95	3.86	129.0
5.00	10.32	4.03	133.8
7.50	10.95	4.38	141.9
10.00	10.95	—	141.9

TABLE V(a)

Liquid paraffin-water-CTAB

Ionic strength = 0.01 (maintained by adding HCl)

Temperature = 30°; $D_{30}^\circ = 76.0$; $\eta_{30}^\circ = 0.008004$ poise $R = 0.485 \times 10^2$ ohms; $i = 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$ amp.

Concentration of CTAB in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^4$	Average U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm. $U_a \times 10^4$	$\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ in gm-ion	ζ in mV
0.66	10.39	1.74	123.8
0.90	11.13	2.18	132.4
1.20	11.98	2.61	142.7
1.80	12.78	3.18	152.3
2.10	13.35	3.48	159.1

TABLE V(b)

Liquid paraffin-water CTAB

Ionic strength = 0.02 (maintained by adding NaCl and HCl in 1 : 1 ratio)

Temperature = 30°; $R = 0.388 \times 10^2$ ohms; $i = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$ ampere

Concentration of CTAB in gm-mole/l. $C \times 10^4$	Average U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm. $U_a \times 10^4$	$\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ in gm-ion	ζ in mV
0.90	8.05	2.39	95.9
1.20	8.30	2.70	98.9
1.50	8.69	3.13	103.5
1.80	9.02	3.57	107.4
2.10	9.24	3.83	110.1
2.40	9.24	4.18	110.1

TABLE VI

n-Heptane-water-CTAB

Ionic strength = 0.01 (maintained by adding HCl)

Temperature = 25°; $R = 0.488 \times 10^2$ ohms; $i = 3.5 \times 10^{-3}$ amp.

Concentration of CTAB in gm-mole/l. $C \times 10^5$	Average U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm. $U_a \times 10^4$	$\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ in gm-ion	ζ in mV
3.61	7.73	2.19	100.2
6.02	8.25	2.63	106.9
8.43	8.85	2.98	114.8
9.64	9.11	3.20	118.1
12.05	9.39	3.42	121.7

TABLE VII(a)

Toluene-water-CTAB

Ionic strength = 0.01 (maintained by adding HCl)

Temperature = 25°; $R = 0.480 \times 10^2$ ohms; $i = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$ amp.

Concentration of CTAB in gm-mole/l. $C \times 10^5$	Average U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm. $U_a \times 10^4$	$\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ in gm-ion	ζ in mV
6.62	9.71	2.28	125.9
7.83	9.95	2.98	129.0
8.43	10.08	3.24	130.6
8.85	10.20	3.42	132.2
9.88	10.30	3.86	133.6
10.30	10.30	3.93	133.6

TABLE VII(b)

Toluene-water-CTAB system

Ionic strength = 0.03 (maintained by adding HCl and NaCl in 1 : 2 ratio)

Temperature = 30°; $R = 0.280 \times 10^2$ ohms. $i = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$ amp.

Concentration of CTAB in gm-mole/l	Average U_a in cm/sec/volt/cm.	$\Gamma \times 10^{10}$ in gm-ion/cm ²	ζ in mV
6.02	7.11	2.16	84.7
6.62	7.35	2.34	87.6
7.83	8.30	2.86	99.2
8.43	8.80	3.24	104.8
9.03	9.50	3.63	113.2
9.66	10.08	3.89	120.0
12.50	10.08		120.0

TABLE VIII

Interface	Long chain electrolyte	Range of conc ⁿ for which ζ -log C relation is linear	Ionic strength
Benzene-water	NaDS	$1.00 \times 10^{-5}M$ to $18.30 \times 10^{-5}M$	0.01
Toluene-water	NaDS	$0.90 \times 10^{-5}M$ to $18.30 \times 10^{-5}M$	0.01
Liquid paraffin-water	NaDS	$2.50 \times 10^{-5}M$ to $12.50 \times 10^{-5}M$	0.01
<i>n</i> -Heptane-water	NaDS	$1.50 \times 10^{-4}M$ to $7.50 \times 10^{-4}M$	0.01
Liquid paraffin-water	CTAB	$0.66 \times 10^{-4}M$ to $2.10 \times 10^{-4}M$	0.01
<i>n</i> -Heptane-water	CTAB	$3.61 \times 10^{-5}M$ to $12.05 \times 10^{-5}M$	0.01
Toluene-water	CTAB	$6.62 \times 10^{-5}M$ to $10.30 \times 10^{-5}M$	0.01
Liquid paraffin-water	CTAB	$0.90 \times 10^{-4}M$ to $2.40 \times 10^{-4}M$	0.02
Toluene-water	CTAB	$6.02 \times 10^{-5}M$ to $9.66 \times 10^{-5}M$	0.03

DISCUSSION

It may be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables I to VII that the values of U_a increases gradually with the increase in molar concentration of the long chain ion at constant ionic strength.

The values of U_a , ζ and Γ for different O/W interfaces are presented in the Tables I to VII. A linear relationship between ζ and Γ has been noticed within the range of concentration investigated. A steady increase of the electrophoretic mobilities as well as of the zeta-potentials with the increase in molar concentration of the long chain ion is observed for all the systems investigated. It will be noticed that as the ionic strength increases the value of U_a diminishes appreciably [Tables V(a), V(b), VII(a) and VII(b)].

It is observed that ζ plotted against $\log C$ yields a straight line over a certain range of concentration of long chain ion investigated. The range of concentration for which this linearity between ζ and $\log C$ holds are recorded in the Table VIII.

It follows from Verwey and Overbeek's¹⁴ theory that when $\psi_0 > 100$ mV, and

$$\rho \text{ (i.e. charge density)} = en$$

where n is the no. of long chain ions adsorbed per unit area of the interface and is equal to $\Gamma \times N$, where N is the Avogadro number

then

$$\rho = \text{constant.} \quad \sqrt{C_t} \cdot \exp \frac{e \psi_0}{2 kT} = en \quad \dots (1)$$

or

$$\exp. \frac{e \psi_0}{2 kT} = \frac{en}{\text{const.} \sqrt{C_t}}$$

where C_t = total concentration of the electrolytes

14. E. J. W. Verwey and J. Th. G. Overbeek, "Theory of the Stability of Lyophobic Colloids", Elsevier, Amsterdam (1948).

$$\text{or} \quad \psi_0 = \frac{2kT}{e} \ln \frac{\text{const.}}{\sqrt{C_t}} + \frac{2kT}{e} \ln n \quad \dots \quad (1b)$$

Here, ψ_0 = electrochemical potential and other terms have their usual significance.

It is known that Freundlich isotherm in the form $n = KC^{1/3}$ holds for the adsorption of a long chain ion over a moderate range of its concentration in the aqueous phase^{10,11,15,16}. If this relation is assumed to hold for the systems investigated, then,

$$\ln n = \frac{1}{3} \ln C + \ln K$$

Putting this value of $\ln n$ in equation (1b), we get,

$$\psi_0 = \frac{2kT}{e} \ln \frac{\text{const.}}{\sqrt{C_t}} + \frac{2kT}{e} \ln K + \frac{2}{3} \frac{kT}{e} \ln C \quad \dots \quad (1c)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \psi_0 = \text{const.} + \frac{2RT}{3F} \ln C \quad \dots \quad (1d)$$

Since the first term in the R.H.S. of equation (1b) is constant for a definite ionic strength maintained by adding a neutral electrolyte we may write the equation (1d) as

$$\frac{\psi_0 - \zeta}{\zeta} + \frac{\zeta}{\zeta} = \frac{\text{const.}}{\zeta} + \frac{2RT}{3F\zeta} \ln C \quad \dots \quad (1e)$$

$$\text{Putting} \quad \frac{\psi_0 - \zeta}{\zeta} = P,$$

where $\psi_0 - \zeta$ = potential of the Stern layer,

ζ = potential of the diffuse double layer,

the equation (1e) can be written in the following form

$$(P+1) = \frac{\text{const.}}{\zeta} + \frac{2RT}{3F\zeta} \ln C \quad \dots \quad (1f)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \zeta = \frac{\text{const.}}{(P+1)} + \frac{2RT}{3(P+1)F} \ln C \quad \dots \quad (1g)$$

$$= \text{const.} + \frac{2RT}{3(P+1)F} \ln C \quad \dots \quad (1h)$$

Since the relation between ζ and $\ln C$ is linear it appears that within the range of concentrations of the long chain ions investigated the ratio of the Stern layer potential and ζ -potential remains constant.

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Department of Chemistry,
University College of Science,
Calcutta-9.

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16. L. Kundu, Thesis (University of Calcutta), unpublished, 1969.